

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES IN OXIDATION—REDUCTION REACTIONS. PART II. OXIDATION WITH POTASSIUM IODATE.

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Fenwick (*Dissertation, Ann Arbor, 1922, p. 76*) studied the oxidation of thiocyanate with iodate in the presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid using the polarised bimetallic system. In Part I of this series (Singh and Ilahi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 717) the authors have shown that thalious chloride, stannous chloride, mercurous chloride, potassium, antimonyl formate and arsenious oxide can be determined potentiometrically by titrating against standard potassium iodate in presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid. In the present investigation the work has been extended to estimate potassium thiocyanate, sodium tetrathionate, hydrazine sulphate, potassium permanganate and potassium dichromate following the same experimental technique.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A known weight of each salt was weighed into a titration vessel and the required amount of concentrated hydrochloric acid added to keep its concentration above 4 *N*. Standard potassium iodate was added from a burette, the mixture stirred by a mechanical stirrer and the progress of the oxidation followed with the potentiometer.

For the estimations of potassium dichromate and potassium permanganate, a known weight of each salt was mixed with a known excess of potassium iodide solution and the required amount of hydrochloric acid. The excess of potassium iodide was determined by titrating the mixture potentiometrically against standard potassium iodate.

A series of potentiometric titrations were performed with different amounts of each salt. One titration for every salt, as typical of that set is recorded in the following tables.

TABLE I.

Titration of K-thiocyanate (0.0323 g.) mixed with 20 c.c. of water and 25 c. c. of conc. HCl against KIO_3 ($M/10$).

KIO_3 .	E. M. F. (volts).	E/C (m. volt/c.c.).
4.00 c.c.	0.552	50
4.20	0.562	65
4.40	0.575	85
4.60	0.592	90
4.80	0.610	110
4.90	0.621	160
4.95	0.629	<u>5140</u>
5.00	0.886	120
5.05	0.892	110
5.15	0.903	85
5.35	0.920	40
5.85	0.940	13
6.85	0.953	6
8.85	0.965	—

TABLE II.

Titration of Na-tetrathionate (0.0270 g.) mixed with 20 c. c. of water and 25 c. c. of conc. HCl. against KIO_3 ($M/20$).

KIO_3 .	E. M. F. (volts)	E/C (m. volt/c.c.).
5.00 c.c.	0.586	16
6.00	0.602	20
6.20	0.606	35
6.40	0.613	40
6.60	0.621	50
6.80	0.631	80
6.90	0.639	120
6.95	0.645	<u>4120</u>
7.00	0.851	200
7.05	0.861	160
7.10	0.869	90
7.20	0.878	55
7.40	0.889	30
7.90	0.904	9
8.50	0.913	

TABLE III.

Titration of hydrazine sulphate (0.1301 g.) mixed with 20 c.c. of water and 25 c. c. of conc. HCl against KIO_3 ($M/10$).

KIO_3 .	E. M. F. (volts).	E/C (m. volt/c.c.).	KIO_3 .	E. M. F. (volts).	E/C (m. volt/c.c.).
8.00 c.c.	0.595	18	9.95 c.c.	0.694	<u>3620</u>
9.00	0.613	20	10.00	0.875	140
9.20	0.617	40	10.05	0.882	110
9.40	0.625	50	10.15	0.893	60
9.60	0.635	61	10.35	0.925	29
9.80	0.647	280	10.80	0.918	14
9.90	0.675	380	11.80	0.932	

TABLE IV.

Titration of KMnO_4 (0.0632 g.) mixed with 10 c.c. of water, 40 c.c. of KI ($M/20$) and 60 c.c. of conc. HCl against KIO_3 ($M/20$).

KIO_3 .	E. M. F. (volts).	E/C. (m. volt/c.c.).
8'00 c.c.	0'557	
		16
9'00	0'573	34
9'50	0'590	57
9'80	0'607	70
9'90	0'614	80
9'95	0'618	140
10'00	0'625	4060
10'05	0'828	240
10'10	0'840	120
10'20	0'852	85
10'40	0'860	50
10'90	0'894	14
11'90	0'908	

TABLE V.

Titration of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (0.0915 g.) mixed with 10 c.c. of water, 40 c.c. of KI ($M/20$) and 50 c.c. of conc. HCl against KIO_3 ($M/20$).

KIO_3 .	E. M. F. (volts).	E/C (m. volt/c.c.).
9'50 c.c.	0'544	
		42
10'00	0'565	60
10'20	0'577	75
10'40	0'592	100
10'50	0'602	150
10'60	0'617	220
10'65	0'628	3860
10'70	0'821	180
10'75	0'830	140
10'80	0'837	70
10'90	0'844	60
11'10	0'856	22
11'60	0'867	

The curves for the above titrations are given in Fig. 1.

DISCUSSION.

In these titrations, with the addition of standard potassium iodate, the E.M.F. rose steadily till the equivalence-point. At the equivalence-point, there was a sharp jump in potential in each case. For the addition of 0.05 c.c. of the titrant, the inflection potential was of the order of 257, 206, 181, 203 and 193 millivolts for potassium thiocyanate, sodium tetrathionate, hydrazine sulphate, potassium permanganate, and potassium dichromate respectively. After the equivalence-point, there was again a rise in the potential which became steady on further addition of the reagent.

FIG. 1.

Curves 1—5 refer respectively to K-thiocyanate, Na-tetrathionate, hydrazine sulphate, KMnO_4 and $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$.

From the volume of the potassium iodate solution required in each titration, corresponding to the equivalence-point, the amount of the each salt was calculated. The values obtained are compared with the amounts of the salt taken in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Potassium thiocyanate.		Sodium tetrathionate.		Hydrazine sulphate.	
Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
0.0323 g.	0.0322 g.	0.0270 g.	0.0269 g.	0.1301 g.	0.1299 g.
0.0685	0.0684	0.0540	0.0541	0.2168	0.2167
0.0921	0.0922	0.0712	0.0712	0.3892	0.3890
0.1182	0.1181	0.1081	0.1082	0.4731	0.4732

TABLE VI (contd.).

Potassium permanganate.

KMnO_4 (taken).	KI (M/20) (added).	KIO_3 (M/20) (used).	KI (M/20) (used for permanganate).	KMnO_4 (found).
0.0632 g.	40 c.c.	10.03 c.c.	19.94 c.c.	0.0630 g
0.0807	50	12.25	25.50	0.0806
0.0946	60	15.03	29.94	0.0946
0.1132	65	14.58	35.84	0.1133

Potassium dichromate,

$\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (taken).	KI (M/20) (added).	KIO_3 (M/20) (used).	KI (M/20) (used for dichromate).	$\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (found).
0.0915 g.	40 c.c.	10.68 c.c.	18.64 c.c.	0.0914 g.
0.1225	50	12.52	24.96	0.1224
0.0490	30	9.98	10.04	0.0492
0.0733	30	7.53	14.94	0.0732

The above results show that potassium thiocyanate, sodium tetrathionate, hydrazine sulphate, potassium permanganate and potassium dichromate can be accurately determined by the potentiometric method.

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